

This folder includes the Supplements to : **Source scaling and ground motion variability along the East Anatolian Fault**, D. Bindi, R. Zaccarelli, F. Cotton, G. Weatherill, S. R. Kotha. published by The Seismic Record.

Supplements include the following 8 files:

git_attenuation.csv – table (using , as separator) reporting the spectral attenuation for different frequencies; distances in km are provided in the first column (dist), the subsequent columns provide the attenuation for different frequencies indicated by the column name;

git_source.csv – table (using ; as separator) providing the non-parametric source spectra; frequencies are reported in the first column (freq), the name of the other columns is the event identifier (see also table_source_parameters.csv);

git_site.csv – table (separator ;) including the relative site amplifications obtained through the GIT decomposition; frequencies are reported in the first column (freq), the name of the other columns identifies the station (network_name_channel);

git_amplification_reference.csv – amplification model used to constrain the average amplification of the reference stations;

git_selected_ref_stations.csv – list of stations selected as reference (i.e., their average amplification has been constrained to the model given in git_amplification_reference.csv);

gmm_fas_coeff.csv - coefficients of the ground motion model in equation (6);

gmm_fas_sigmas.csv - standard deviation of the ground motion model in equation (6).

table_source_parameters.csv – this table reports the source parameters:

ID – event identifier for this study

mo – log₁₀ of seismic moment [Nm]

dmo – standard error on mo (set to NA for those events with mo constrained using Mw in the AFAD catalog);

fc – corner frequency [Hz]

dfc- standard error on corner frequency

errfit – root mean square error of the fit

mw – moment magnitude computed from mo

semw- error on mw

stressdropMPa – stress drop in MPa

vsdepth – shear wave velocity used for computing the stress drop, in km/s

ev_id_afad – event identifier in the AFAD catalog

ev_otime – origin time in the AFAD catalog

ev_lat – event latitude in the AFAD catalog

ev_lon – event longitude in the AFAD catalog

ev_dep_km – depth in the AFAD catalog

ev_mag – magnitude in the AFAD catalog

ev_mty – magntiude type in the AFAD catalog